

Death prediction for Adult Diabetes Patients

Ching Yin Wan¹, Youran Zhou¹, Mukhammad Karimov¹, and Kartik Mahendra Jalal¹

¹The University of Melbourne, ¹Email: {chingyi, youran, jalalk, mkarimov}@student.unimelb.edu.au

Abstract

In 2021, an estimated 537 million people globally were living with diabetes, contributing to 6.7 million deaths that year (International Diabetes Federation, 2022). The disease is associated with severe complications such as blindness, heart attacks, coronary artery disease, and stroke^{5,6}. Accurately assessing the mortality risk for patients with diabetes is therefore critical for public health planning. This project aims to predict the likelihood of mortality among diabetic patients using the MIMIC-IV dataset⁴. We evaluate four machine learning and deep learning models for binary classification of patient survival. Performance is assessed using standard evaluation metrics, with random forest outperforming the others across all criteria. To enhance interpretability, we conduct a feature importance analysis to identify which clinical factors most strongly influence mortality risk in diabetic patients.

Key words: Diabetes, MIMIC-IV, supervised learning, mortality rate, interpretable machine learning.

1 INTRODUCTION

As of 2021, an estimated 537 million people worldwide are affected by diabetes, with the disease causing approximately 6.7 million deaths globally². Diabetes is linked to serious complications such as blindness, heart attacks⁶, and increased risks of coronary artery disease and stroke⁵. Given its widespread impact and severity, understanding the mortality risk associated with diabetes is of critical importance.

In this project, we analyze data from the MIMIC-IV clinical database⁴ to predict the likelihood of mortality among diabetic patients. We applied both machine learning and deep learning classifiers to perform binary classification tasks and evaluated model performance using standard assessment metrics. A feature importance analysis was conducted to interpret the best-performing model and identify key predictors of mortality.

Chapter 1 introduces the background and data source. Chapter 2 outlines our methodology, including the use of interpretable models (Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbors, Explainable Boosting Classifier, Random Forest) and a neural network (Multi-Layer Perceptron). In Chapter 3, we present evaluation results across multiple dimensions. Chapter 4 offers a detailed feature analysis and a comparison between interpretable models and the black-box model. The source code is included in the Appendix.

2 METHODS

This section outlines the methods used to perform digital phenotyping, define the patient cohort, and extract relevant features from the MIMIC-IV dataset. We also describe the pipeline for the binary classification task.

2.1 Digital Phenotyping

We selected MIMIC-IV as the dataset for digital phenotyping. It contains de-identified health records of patients admitted to a medical center, with all individuals aged 18 years or older. To define diabetes cases, we followed the diagnostic criteria for diabetes mellitus in adults as outlined by UpToDate³.

The diagnostic criteria include fasting plasma glucose (FPG), plasma glucose, glycated hemoglobin (A1C), and symptoms of hyperglycemia. Among these, only A1C values are explicitly represented in MIMIC-IV. Using A1C values alone could result in overly inclusive phenotyping, potentially misclassifying non-diabetic patients. Prior studies using MIMIC-III (e.g.,¹) have also relied on hemoglobin A1c and mean glucose levels, while omitting plasma glucose measurements.

To strengthen specificity and reflect best practices, we incorporated both A1C and blood glucose values as diagnostic criteria. For this study, blood glucose is treated as equivalent to plasma glucose.

A patient is classified as diabetic if **both** of the following conditions are met:

- **Blood glucose ≥ 200 mg/dL:** At least one recorded blood glucose item must have a `valuenum` of 200 or greater.
- **A1C value $\geq 6.5\%$:** The `valuenum` of the A1C item must be at least 6.5.

Applying these criteria, we identified **16,351 patients** with diabetes.

Table 1 presents the MIMIC-IV item IDs used in the digital phenotyping process, along with their total frequency in the dataset and the number of patients meeting the corresponding thresholds.

Table 1. Patient diagnosis criteria

Item name	Table name	Item ID	Unit	Frequency	# Patients
% Hemoglobin A1c	d_labitems	50852	%	235,348	22,013
Glucose	d_labitems	50809	mg/dL	221,767	10,444
Glucose	d_labitems	50931	mg/dL	2,893,059	40,232
Glucose (whole blood)	d_items	226537	mg/dL	156,736	5,571

2.2 Label and feature extraction

To determine whether a diabetes patient died due to the condition, we used the **dod** column from the **patients** table in the hospital module as our outcome label. This column indicates the in-hospital, de-identified date of death for each patient⁴. Patients with a non-null **dod** value were labeled as 1 (deceased), while those with a null value (i.e., **NaT**) were labeled as 0 (survived).

In addition to the outcome label, we extracted features including insurance, language, marital status, race, total number of admissions, gender, anchor age, anchor year, anchor year group, average hospital stay duration (in hours), mean glucose level, and mean A1C value during hospitalization. The first ten features were obtained from the **chartevents**, **labevents**, and **patients** tables in both the hospital and ICU modules, while the final four features were derived via feature engineering.

2.3 Preliminary analysis and dataset splitting

During preliminary analysis, we found the dataset to be imbalanced, with only about 26% of records labeled as death. No missing data was identified. Since the extracted features were either nominal or numerical, we applied a nominal-to-numerical encoding scheme to transform categorical data. We then standardized all features using **StandardScaler**, which removes the mean and scales the data to unit variance.

We employed a holdout strategy to split the dataset into 80% training and 20% test subsets for model development and evaluation.

2.4 Models

We trained three interpretable machine learning models: K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Logistic Regression (LR), and Random Forest (RF). As an ensemble method, Random Forest was expected to yield superior performance among the traditional classifiers.

To further improve model interpretability, we incorporated the Explainable Boosting Machine (EBM), a glass-box model that balances performance and explainability. Additionally, we implemented a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) as a representative deep learning model. Given the expressive power of neural networks, we expected the MLP to deliver strong predictive results.

Figure 1. Feature importance from the Random Forest model

Hyperparameter tuning was performed for all models using grid search cross-validation to optimize performance.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Model evaluation results

Table 2 shows the evaluation results for each model. For each evaluation metric, the best result has been highlighted. It can be seen that the Random Forest model outperforms every other model. For all models, the recall is lower than precision, indicating that all models might have a weaker ability to find all of the dead patients. This could be explained due to the dataset being imbalanced: There is an insufficient number of dead patients, so the models could not fully learn the main characteristics of deceased individuals. Figure 1 provides the ROC plot. As previously mentioned, a larger AUC indicates better classification performance. The plot shows that the Random Forest model has the largest AUC, which indicates that it has the best performance among all models.

Unexpectedly, the Logistic Regression model, one of the most interpretable models, does not have a strong performance. It is possible that the dataset does not meet the assumptions required for performing logistic regression, which includes independent observations, a linear relationship between the logit and independent variables, and the absence of highly correlated independent variables.

Table 2. Model evaluation results

Evaluation metrics	KNN	LR	MLP	EBM	RF
Train accuracy	0.87	0.77	0.82	0.80	1.00
Test accuracy	0.76	0.78	0.78	0.80	0.88
Precision (Death)	0.56	0.66	0.63	0.71	0.89
Recall (Death)	0.45	0.36	0.48	0.45	0.65
F1 (Death)	0.50	0.47	0.55	0.55	0.75
Balanced Accuracy	0.66	0.65	0.69	0.69	0.81
MCC	0.34	0.37	0.41	0.45	0.69
AUC	0.66	0.65	0.69	0.69	0.81

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 Feature Importance

As established in Chapter 3, the Random Forest model achieved the best classification performance among all models tested. To further investigate the factors contributing to mortality among diabetic patients, we conducted a feature importance analysis.

Feature importance scores reflect the relative contribution of each variable to the model’s decision-making process. While these scores vary across models, the superior performance of the Random Forest suggests that its feature rankings are particularly reliable and informative. The top-ranked features identified by the model were **mean_stay**, **total_admissions**, **mean_glucose**, and **mean_a1c**, all of which are indicative of disease severity.

We also compared these results with those from the Explainable Boosting Classifier (EBC), and found a high level of consistency between the two models. In both cases, longer hospital stays, a greater number of admissions, and elevated glucose and A1C levels were associated with increased disease severity and a higher risk of death.

Patient age was also found to be a significant factor influencing mortality risk. However, based on the feature importance plots alone, we could not determine a clear directional relationship—i.e., whether older patients are more likely to die.

In contrast, demographic variables such as race, marital status, and gender appeared to have minimal influence on the model’s predictions. These personal attributes did not show significant differences in mortality outcomes across patient groups.

4.2 Model Comparison

Surprisingly, the Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) model did not perform as well as expected. Overall, the MLP and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) models yielded similar evaluation results. This relatively low performance may indicate underfitting, as deep neural networks typically require large volumes of data to generalize effectively. The current dataset size may not have been sufficient to train the MLP model adequately.

Figure 2. Feature importance from the Random Forest model

5 CONCLUSION

This project aimed to predict the likelihood of mortality among diabetic patients using data from the MIMIC-IV database⁴. We first performed digital phenotyping to construct a patient cohort from MIMIC-IV. Subsequently, we applied four machine learning models and one deep learning model to carry out a binary classification task.

Among the models tested, the Random Forest classifier demonstrated the best performance, achieving an AUC greater than 0.8. Feature importance analysis further revealed that no specific demographic group is particularly prone to mortality due to diabetes. However, indicators of disease severity—such as glucose and A1C levels—as well as patient age, were found to have a strong influence on mortality risk.

For future work, a larger dataset could be used to mitigate the underfitting observed in the MLP model. Additional clinical features, such as fasting plasma glucose (FPG) and other lab measurements, could also be included. Moreover, a broader range of machine learning models could be explored to enhance predictive performance.

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Figure 3. Feature importance from the Explainable Boosting Classifier

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